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Influence of Technological Advancement on Innovation of Automobile Industry in Kenya

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Abstract

The study sought to find the influence of technological advancement on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. The study established that innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya was significantly influenced by the technological knowledge and skills of the work force, creativity of the work force, and technological patent. The analysis was done by applying Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Version 25). According to the bivariate analysis, the coefficient of correlation "r" for Technological advancement is equal to 0.824 ($P=0.000$), Creativity of the work force is equal to 0.804 ($p=0.000$), and Technological patents is equal to 0.873 ($P=0.000$). This demonstrates that the dependent variable (Innovation of automobile industry) and the independent variables have positive significance. The multiple regression analysis table 5. Shows that $R=87.8\%$. The validity model shown in table 5 indicates that the model is valid ($F=165.432$, $P=000$) implying that it can be used for purposes of prediction. The coefficient model shows the following in table 5: Technological skills, 15.1 % ($B=0.151$), Creativity of work force, 14.1 % ($B=0.141$), Technological patents 75.5% ($B=0.755$). Otherwise all independent variables (Technological skills, Creativity and Technological patents) remaining constant innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya remains at constant (15.4%, $B=0.154$). This therefore underscores that all null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted since the independent variables in the study positively influence innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

Key words: Technological skills of the work force, Creativity of the work force, Technological patents, Lack of research and development, Innovation of the automobile industry

1-Introduction

Innovation of organizations is very important and complicated characteristics firms are faced in the contemporary globe. Innovativeness crucially impact establishment's performance together with viability. In order for an organization to achieve competitiveness to surpass its competitors increase its penetration of the market by the production of modern and distinctive goods for customers, it must be innovative. Profitability will be increased when an organization possesses the capability of innovation. Innovation is a characteristic which strongly dictates its performance. (Shaharoun et al., 2019). According to Santos and Pavarotti (2018) on the innovative process in the automobile sector. Innovation process management is well articulated by co-creation as transformational innovation, and by innovation that is developed internally by a firm. The information from the study guided the creation, growth and application of many automobiles emanating from international

frameworks, having domestic technological establishment centre's programs. In view of that fact, the transformation paradigm within the domestic motor vehicle group participation forms a modification that was derived from research and development. Lango and Muchiri, (2020) observed that, development of international markets caused firms to undertake the role of innovation in development. It becomes necessary for establishments to plan their space to innovate in a changing world which is evolving rapidly and experiencing persistent shifts unpredictability. The idea regarding innovation clarity has to be distinguished to be recently developed administration order, plan of action, attribute, or technique, recently developed manufacturing activity, or recent output by a firm. The key drivers of strategic innovation management practices are; strategy of innovation, institutional framework, innovation culture, scientific knowledge and consumer dealer interactions resulting into high efficiency.

According to Begum A. (2018) the development and advancement in technology has significantly improved our lifestyle. Technology has made its impact on nearly all the dimensions of life. The rate of technological advancement is increasing with time, society is looking to create and develop easier ways to live and lengthen their lives. The internet is a massive source of information that millions of people use and depend on every day. The advancement of new technology has been taking place since the beginning of human history. The rate of technological advancement is increasing with time, society is looking to create and develop easier ways to live and lengthen their lives. Development is closely related with technology. The radical change and advancement in the economy, as we observe today, is the result of the modern technology. Technology has brought about efficiency and quality in the manufacturing sector.

Showi, (2018), additionally observed that the advancement of the automotive sector can be traced back to the year 1808, when the earliest car that used a heat engine in where combustion occurred in the engine and powered by hydrogen. It was regarded as the first production since Benz made many other similar copies. With the enlargement in number of production space, the automotive sector is also adding to the employment chances, contributing in satisfying the employment requirements of a young nation. Shaikh, (2013) stated that, the automotive sector basically flourished from World War II (1938-1945), for supplying automobiles used in the war. Since then, motor vehicle design experienced the total radical changes. Motor vehicle design and production finally came from the military inclination and other shadow of war in 1949. The sector kept on prospering at an amazing rate of innovative ideas and initiation of new technology. Wellbrock et. al., (2020). Stated that, the success of the automobile sector is enabled by constant strategies of innovation, building brand names, international effectiveness in the supply linkage and expertise and a well-motivated workforce. Wellbrock considered Research and development as the key to the success of technological innovations the automobile industry globally.

Kenya formulated vision 2030 as a guide to industrialization. This was induced by the sustainable development goals that enhance the realization of vision 2030. Industrialization takes place where there is technological innovation space, engagement of research and development activities and the use of the motor vehicle technology diffused into the country. Bharawadwaj (2015) stated that the motor vehicle sector is changing in different directions; scientific knowledge, accommodation of tough state regulatory frameworks and organizational modifications together with dynamic customer requirements. The automotive sector supports every section of any community. In many nations, the automotive sector is a pillar of wealth development granting remarkably to Gross Domestic Product and to treasury Kenya has also diffused, commercialized and managed automobile technology over the years before and after independence. There have been some effective attempts to innovate and commercialize the automobile industry in Kenya. Mobias and the Nyayo car have been developed and produced in Kenya, only that they have not entered the global market. These interventions have not had any significant effect.

2. Research objectives

The objectives of the study include: to determine the influence of the technological knowledge and skills of the work force on innovation of the automobile industry, to evaluate the influence of creativity of the work force on

innovation of the automobile industry, and to examine the influence of technological patents on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

3. Literature review

Bharawadwaj (2015) conducted a study at OP Jindal Global University, Jindal Global Law School, India, examining economic, socio and Technological challenges within international auto sector. The research sheds light on the challenges confronting international auto sector and underscores the pivotal role of technological innovation in facilitating the industry's ability to adapt to change. The study also enlightens on some current technologies in this area implemented during tight environmental policies. The automotive industry involves every section of any society. The auto sector has served as a major economic engine and contributes significantly to GDP and to the exchequer of many economies in the world. The automobile sector is experiencing changes at a very fast pace, from product variation, fuel usage, environmental safety, ease of use, and cost are all priorities. The automobile sector is developing rapidly on many aspects; innovation in technology, robust government rules, and structural shifts with changeable customer preferences. Recently, with the developing climate change and the concerns of human health, large investments are being directed into the sector to solve the twin problems of pollution and efficiency of fuel usage.

Ritter and Gemünden (2004) noted that the success of innovation is pegged on research and development activities in firms. The growing costs of innovation, the duration of innovation and the radical and incremental innovation technology complexities have increased the research and development activities. Two camps that were brought forth by the author are to examine the inner factors of success of innovations by scrutinizing the process of innovation and organizational culture and to evaluate the set of dependent variables existing in the internal environment of the organization. The effect of partnership in the success of innovation is different in the different stages of innovation. Having the twin areas for upgrades in the success of innovation, it is of paramount importance to scrutinize the effect on which fundamental competencies are based on. Both the growth of competence and success of innovation are functions corporate strategy of technology in firms.

Kalko (2022) delved into the realm of techniques related with management of technology and creativity in Ethiopian medium- as well as large-scale production companies. The research considered The effects of the techniques of managing technologies on success in innovation, including past experiences and multimodal characteristics. It investigated the impact of technological processes, acquisition, transfer, and absorption on innovation. The study found that technology transfer played a crucial role in driving product, process, and method innovations. Furthermore, technology process, acquisition, and absorption were valuable factors that significantly influenced innovation and had positive effects on process and method innovation.

Mormina (2019) examined innovation, technology, science, as social items from Sen's Capabilities Approach. The study framed scientific knowledge as a social good and emphasized the importance of strengthening social structures for knowledge production. It argued for a holistic approach to research capacity building, beyond individual skills training, focusing on creating environments conducive to knowledge production. Scientific knowledge distribution and building scientific capacity in developing countries were recognized as essential for development cooperation. The research underscored the significance of institutions in nurturing environments conducive to the generation and dissemination of collective scientific knowledge and resources, fostering economic, technological, and social innovation, including commercialization.

Tang et al., 2010 investigated the influence of technical creativity on invention achievement: a theoretical investigation in Hong Kong and discovered that different technological innovation capabilities have different effects on different performance measures. Organizational capability had the most significant effect. So as to cope with this change, good capability in organizing different activities among different departments is crucial to the favourable outcome of a company. Many researchers have found that technological innovation could create favourable effects and improve their competitiveness.

Lee et al. (2018) conducted a study analyzing the consequences of technological and scientific advances confluence on creativity, particularly in the context of the U.S. pharmaceutical industry. The research investigated using patent data, they may examine the connection between confluence and creativity. The study

also considered mediating factors such as organizational capabilities, knowledge spillover, and the nature of knowledge. It explored how a firm's scientific capacity influenced the effect of innovation resulting from convergence. Additionally, the study looked at scientific knowledge maturity and the role of the research environment in facilitating knowledge exchange among researchers. The research concluded that convergence between technology and science significantly impacted innovation, with the effect varying based on the ratio of scientific to technological knowledge. It also found that a conducive research environment with increased interaction among researchers facilitated innovation.

Adak (2015) conducted research analyzing the impact of technical advancement and creativity on the economy of Turkey. The study utilized data from various sources, including the OECD, World Bank, Turkish Patent Institute, and the Turkish Statistical Institute. The research employed a two-stage model, with the first stage focusing on innovation and the second stage incorporating innovation into an aggregate production function. The study revealed a significant positive impact of technological growth and innovation on economic development.

Yu et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between economic liberalization, intellectual property protection, and regional innovation in Chinese provinces. The study aimed to analyze the impact of international trade and intellectual property rights protection on regional innovation, using a provincial panel database. The results indicated that increased general trade and higher exports and imports relative to GDP had significant and positive impacts on provincial innovation in China. Moreover, enhanced intellectual property protection was found to stimulate economic benefits of innovation in each region, leading to increased investments in research and development. The findings also suggested that expanded export opportunities and import competition motivated Chinese regions to invest more in innovation and develop their technology through exports, rather than relying solely on the importation of foreign technology.

Methodology

Philosophy of the study

Study philosophies can be positivism, interpretivism, or pragmatism. Positivism, in its understanding of the world, operates on the premise that the external environment and the events of interest are objective entities, situated outside of and detached from the researcher, as asserted by Saunders et al. (2009). Positivism shows the belief that reality is firm and can be examined and explained from the objective point view unaccompanied by interfering with phenomena (Cresswell, Positivism is be considered the most specific technique for this research since it is appropriate for quantitative investigations as it is directed at describing causes which impact results and gives a bases for forecasting and generalization.

In the course of this study, the researcher opted for a survey research design, coupled with the application of bivariate and multiple regression analysis. The fundamental objective of such designs is, indeed, to establish a connection between variables, delineate the nature of this relationship, and quantify the extent of association between two variables. Specifically, multiple regression analysis will be harnessed to forecast the magnitude of the dependent variable. A survey design is appropriate for this study since data can be collected from respondents within various set ups of similar characteristic's in terms of their attitudes, perceptions, opinions, behaviours, or values (Sounders, 2012). This study employed a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches in both data collection and analysis. As emphasized by Babbie (2010), the utilization of both quantitative and qualitative techniques fortifies the research endeavor. These approaches serve to articulate and direct the focus toward objective measurements and the quantitative evaluation of data. The variables of this study included: to determine the influence of the firm's vision on innovation of the automobile industry, to evaluate the influence of the firm's mission on innovation of the automobile industry, to examine the influence of firm's organizational strategy on innovation of the automobile industry, and to investigate the influence of firm's management strategy on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. This study's target population was 139 automobile firms each having four members in this category: CEOs, Technical persons, Finance

Managers and Sales managers forming a population of 556 members. The sampling frame for the target population will be automobile firms in Nairobi, Mombasa and Kisumu cities and Thika town. Stratified sampling technic was applied on automobile dealers. The dealers were stratified into four strata namely Nairobi City, Mombasa City, Kisumu and Thika Town. Random samples were chosen from each stratum employing the stratified sampling technique, with the sample size for each stratum determined by its proportion to the overall population and a systematic sampling technique was applied to select approximately a sample of 30% of the population as given by (Mugenda & Mugenda 2003). In alignment with Mugenda and Mugenda, Kothari (2004) advocated for the suitability of a sample size ranging from 10% to 30%. Opting for a well-selected sample size of 30% facilitates meticulous observations and precise measurements, offering a higher level of accuracy compared to conducting research on a larger pool of automobile firms. This approach ensures that every automobile firm in every city and town has a known and equal likelihood of selection. To determine the sample size, the calculation was as follows: 30% of 131 amounts to 39, which, when added to the 9 assemblers, resulted into a total sample size of 48 automobile firms. Consequently, the sample was comprised of 48 automobile firms drawn from a pool of 131 dealers and 9 assemblers. Each firm will produce the chief executive officer, the technical manager, the finance manager, and sales manager. This will result in 192 respondents who cut across the automobile firm's organizational structure and therefore understood the aspects of enterprise capabilities and innovation of automobile industry.

Consistency of study instrument is the level where a testing of event gives compatible and firm results. Even so, reliability of instrument also deals with itself all the time (Moser & Kalton, 2017). High internal consistency reliability is achieved when the items on a scale align and assess the same underlying construct (Robinson, 2019). The Cronbach Alpha Coefficient is a popular metric of consistency within, especially when Likert scales are used. An internal consistency coefficient of at least 0.70 is desirable. Validity pertains to the extent to which these instruments effectively measure what they purport to measure or were originally designed to assess. It's important to note that reliability, on its own, falls short in ensuring the effectiveness of an assessment tool. A valid instrument is one which tests what is intended to test (Gliner et.al. 2016). Validity of a study instrument will be measured for internal Cronbach's Alpha based on a 70% level of acceptance was used to ensure consistency. This study strategy will satisfy standards of reliability and validity, yielding data that are both consistent (reliability) and correct (validity).

Pre-testing is testing a study instrument on a small sample of respondents singled out by the investigator before a full research is carried out, so as to identify any challenges e.g., unclear choice of words or the questionnaire taking a long time to be executed. Pretesting was done in Malindi Town. The researcher made adjustments to the questionnaires to withdraw ambiguity and double meanings after piloting. Adding to that, changes of the completion time for the questionnaire was made. During this procedure of data collection all ethical values regarding anonymity, confidentiality and respect of the respondents were highly considered by the researcher.

Quantitative data were entered into Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25 (SPSS) so as to run descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency and percentages. To assess the degree of association between two variables Pearson correlation and regression analysis were performed as emphasized by Casson and Farmer (2014). A correlation coefficient (r), served as an indicator of the relationship between the two variables under scrutiny. ANOVA f test was applied to determine if there are statistically significant differences of two or more means. The relationship between corporate strategy and innovation of automobile firms from the obtained data, multiple linear regression analysis was applied. Mugenda and Mugenda (2012) stated that, such analysis endeavours to determine whether a set of variables foresee a particular dependent variable and in this way, strives to increase the accuracy of the estimate. Because this research has four independent factors, multiple regression model was applied. Innovation of automobile industry, was regressed against on four corporate strategies variables namely, firm vision, firm mission, organizational strategy and management strategy. The study conducted a multiple regression model and used it to predict the extent to which each of the four independent variables (X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , and X_4) and the one moderating variable (Z_1) influenced the dependent variable (Y).

The research assessed the normality of the regression model to determine if the assumptions regarding the normal distribution hold true. Shapiro-Wilk statistic was employed to evaluate significance at a threshold of ($p > 0.05$) to confirm whether the distribution is indeed normal. Multicollinearity was applied to determine the relationship of the independent variables.

Findings and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

The study sought to investigate the influence of technology advancement on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

4.2 Demographic characteristics of the respondents and instruments reliability

The study was conducted in Kenya and focused on 48 automobile firms drawn from a pool of 140 such firms and each stratum essentially constituted a scaled-down representation of the overall sample of 48 automobile firms where the respondents were the CEOs, Technical managers, Finance Managers and Sales managers.

Response rate

A total of 151 responses were received out of a target population of 192 respondents. This represented 78.65% response rate and based on this response rate result therefore, it implied that the response rate was adequate for this study.

4.3 Respondents' characteristics

The study sought to determine the respondents' characteristics such as level of education, and period in the industry. The results of respondents' characteristics were presented in as indicated accordingly.

4.3.1 Level of education

The respondents were requested to indicate the highest education. The results show that most of the respondents' highest Level of Education was bachelor degree accounted by 53% followed by diploma 41.7%. Those with post graduate accounted for 5.3% while school certificate showed 0%. This implies that the respondents are well educated and well understand the issues of the influence of enterprise capabilities on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

4.3.2 Period in the industry

The respondents were also requested to indicate how long they have been in the industry. The results show that most (58.30%) of the have been in the industry for period between 1-10 years followed by 10-20 years which accounted for 37.70%.

Reliability instrument

Table 1: Cronbach Alpha for Reliability Assessments

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha Values
Technological knowledge and skills	5	0.757
Creativity of the work force	5	0.711
Technological patents	5	0.793
Innovation of automobile industry	5	0.755

As presented in Table 1, Cronbach alpha values for all the variables; Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity of the work force and Technological patents and Innovation of automobile industry were greater than 0.7. From these results it can be concluded that the constructs measured had the adequate reliability for the subsequent stages of analysis since all the Cronbach Alpha values were greater than 0.7.

Analytical Model Diagnostic Tests

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of Technological advancement on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. A multi linear regression model was specified hence the need to test for assumption underlying its use before using it in data analysis. Analytical model diagnostic tests were carried out as follows;

Table 2: Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Analysis

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Technological skills	.260	3.243
Creativity of the work force	.469	5.168
Technological patents	.363	4.136

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity arises when multiple independent variables in the model are interconnected and offer duplicate information regarding the response variable. To determine how much the variance of predicted coefficients is increased as a result of collinearity between variables that are independent, this study employed Variance Inflation Factors (VIF). The results of Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Analysis for multicollinearity test are presented in Table 2 and is indicating that all the VIF are far less than 10

Table 3: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Technological skills	.597	151	.190	.713	151	.179
Creativity of the work force	.486	151	.120	.628	151	.080
Technological patents	.655	151	.131	.846	151	.210
Innovation of auto-Industry	.376	151	.161	.754	151	.172

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Test of data for normality

Normally data analysis is carried on assumption that data were sampled from a normal distributed data. The testing of data for normality of all the variables under study was done based on Shapiro-wilk (S-W) test and the results were presented in Table 3. The results indicated that the P-value of all the variables was greater than 0.05 (95% confidence level) implying that the variables did not deviate from the normal distribution.

Bivariate Correlation analysis results

Table 4

Variables		Innovation of automobile industry	Technological skills	Creativity	Technological patents
Innovation of automobile industry	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	151			
Technological skills	Pearson Correlation	.824**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	151	151		
Creativity	Pearson Correlation	.804**	.867**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		

	N	151	151	151	
Technological patents	Pearson Correlation	.873**	.909**	.877**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	151	151	151	151

A Bivariate Correlation analysis

The relationship between the study variables and results is depicted in Table 4. of the study's data using Correlation coefficient for Karl Pearson (r). In accordance with the findings, the dependent variable and the independent factors (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity of the work force and Technological patents) (Innovation of automobile industry) have a very significant positive connection. According to the analysis, the coefficient of correlation "r" for Technological advancement is equal to 0.824 (P=0.000), Creativity of the work force is equal to 0.804 (p=0.000), and Technological patents is equal to 0.873 (P=0.000). This demonstrates that the dependent variable (Innovation of automobile industry) and the independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity of the work force and Technological patents) have a highly significant positive association, with Technological patents having the lead. Therefore, it follows that the automobile industry must follow the Technological patents to the later.

Research Hypotheses

- i) **H₁**: Technological knowledge and skills of the work force has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.
- ii) **H₂**: Creativity of the work force has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.
- iii) **H₃**: Technological patents has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

Influence of Technological advancement on innovation of the automobile industry

This research focused in assessing the influence of the various independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity of the work force, and Technological patents) on the dependent variable (Innovation of the automobile industry). To achieve this, a multiple linear regression analysis was performed to test and explain the casual relationships between variables. The multiple linear regression model was composed of both the dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable of the study was on innovation of the automobile industry while the independent variables were; Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity of the work force and Technological patents. The model of the study is as shown in the equation.

Equation 4.1: A Multiple Linear Regression Model One

The multiple linear regression model for the study was as follows;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Y = Innovation of the automobile industry β_0 = constant β_i is the coefficient for X_i (i=1, 2, 3)

X_1 = Technological skills

X_2 = Creativity

X_3 = Technological patents

ε = Error Term

Table 5: Multiple linear regression results

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.878 ^a	.878 ^a	.878 ^a	.771	.878 ^a	.771
a. Predictors: (Constant), Technological skills, Creativity of work force and Technological patents						
Validity model						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	57.775	3	19.258	165.432	.000 ^b
	Residual	17.113	147	.116		
	Total	74.887	150			
a. Dependent Variable: Innovation of the automobile industry						
b. Predictors: (Constant) Technological skills, Creativity of work force and Technological patents						
Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant)	.154	.205		.749	.005
	Technological skills	.151	.122	.125	1.236	.019
	Creativity	.141	.098	.126	1.436	.003
	Technological patents	.755	.122	.650	6.198	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Innovation of the automobile industry						

Results presented in the Table 5 shows that there is a strong relationship ($R=0.878$, $P=0.000$) between enterprise capabilities (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity and Technological patents) and Innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

This means that when enterprise capabilities (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity of work force and Technological patents) are applied by automobile industry in Kenya, its relationship with Innovation of the automobile industry improves by 87.8%.

The validity model indicates that the model is valid ($F=165.432$, $P=000$) implying that it can be used for purposes of prediction. The coefficient model shows that for every unit increase of Technological knowledge and skills, innovation of the automobile industry improves by 15.1 % ($B=0.151$), a unit increase in Creativity of work force, innovation of the automobile industry improves by 14.1 % ($B=0.141$) and a unit increase in Technological patents innovation of the automobile industry improves by 75.5% ($B=0.755$). Otherwise all independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity and Technological patents) remaining constant innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya remains at constant (15.4%, $B=0.154$).

Below are the null hypotheses tested:

Testing of Hypothesis One

H₀: Technological knowledge and skills of the work force has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

The results on table 4. shows a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.824 which is statistically significant ($p<0.05$). This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternate hypothesis that technological knowledge and skills has statistical significance influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. This means that on overall, technological skills is positively related to innovation of the automobile firms in Kenya. The study results correspond with Lee et al. (2018) study who conducted a study analyzing the consequences of technological and scientific advances confluence on creativity, particularly in the context of the U.S. pharmaceutical industry. The research investigated using patent data, examining the connection

between confluence and creativity. The study also considered mediating factors such as organizational capabilities, knowledge spillover, and the nature of knowledge. It explored how a firm's scientific capacity influenced the effect of innovation resulting from convergence. Additionally, the study looked at scientific knowledge maturity and the role of the research environment in facilitating knowledge exchange among researchers. The research concluded that convergence between technology and science significantly impacted innovation, with the effect varying based on the ratio of scientific to technological knowledge. It also found that a conducive research environment with increased interaction among researchers facilitated innovation.

The study results concur with the research done by Mormina (2019) who examined innovation, technology, science, as social items from Sen's Capabilities Approach. The study framed scientific knowledge as a social good and emphasized the importance of strengthening social structures for knowledge production. It argued for a holistic approach to research capacity building, beyond individual skills training, focusing on creating environments conducive to knowledge production. Scientific knowledge distribution and building scientific capacity in developing countries were recognized as essential for development cooperation. The research underscored the significance of institutions in nurturing environments conducive to the generation and dissemination of collective scientific knowledge and resources, fostering economic, technological, and social innovation, including commercialization.

Testing of Hypothesis two

H₀: Creativity of the work force has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

The results on table 4. show a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.804 which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternate hypothesis that creativity of the work force has statistical significance influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. This means that on overall, creativity of the work force is positively related to innovation of the automobile firms in Kenya.

The study results concur with the study by Tang et al., 2010 who investigated the influence of technical creativity on invention achievement: a theoretical investigation in Hong Kong and discovered that different technological innovation capabilities have different effects on different performance measures. Organizational capability had the most significant effect. So as to cope with this change, good capability in organizing different activities among different departments is crucial to the favourable outcome of a company. Many researchers have found that technological innovation could create favourable effects and improve their competitiveness.

The study results also correspond with the study done by Lee et al. (2018) who conducted a study analyzing the consequences of technological and scientific advances confluence on creativity, particularly in the context of the U.S. pharmaceutical industry. It explored how a firm's scientific capacity influenced the effect of innovation resulting from convergence. Additionally, the study looked at scientific knowledge maturity and the role of the research environment in facilitating knowledge exchange among researchers. The research concluded that convergence between technology and science significantly impacted innovation, with the effect varying based on the ratio of scientific to technological knowledge. It also found that a conducive research environment with increased interaction among researchers facilitated innovation.

H₀: Technological patents has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

The results on table 4. show a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.873 which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternate hypothesis that Technological patents has statistical significance influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. This means that on overall, technological patent is positively related to innovation of the automobile firms in Kenya.

Yu et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between economic liberalization, intellectual property protection, and regional innovation in Chinese provinces. The study aimed to analyze the impact of international trade and intellectual property rights protection on regional innovation, using a provincial panel database. The results indicated that increased general trade and higher exports and imports relative to GDP had significant and positive impacts on provincial innovation in China. Moreover, enhanced intellectual property protection was

found to stimulate economic benefits of innovation in each region, leading to increased investments in research and development. The findings also suggested that expanded export opportunities and import competition motivated Chinese regions to invest more in innovation and develop their technology through exports, rather than relying solely on the importation of foreign technology.

The study results also correspond with the study done by Blind 2016 study, the focus was on investigating the impact of regulatory measures on the process of innovation. The study explored the impact of intellectual property rights (IPR) regimes on innovation incentives and disclosure effects. Contrary to expectations, only a handful of studies found favorable effects of rigid international property rights (IPR) regulations on research and development intensity in former G7 nations. In general, investigations into the effects of patents on innovation failed to reveal significant positive effects and sometimes even suggested that patents might deter investment in innovation.

Conclusion

The study was to determine the influence of technological advancement on the innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. The researcher established that (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity and Technological patents) had a significant influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. Shown by the multiple regression analysis table 5. $R=87.8\%$. The validity model shown in table 5 indicates that the model is valid ($F=165.432$, $P=000$) implying that it can be used for purposes of prediction. The coefficient model shows the following in table 5: Technological skills, 15.1% ($B=0.151$), Creativity of work force, 14.1% ($B=0.141$), Technological patents 75.5% ($B=0.755$). Otherwise all independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, Creativity and Technological patents) remaining constant innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya remains at constant (15.4% , $B=0.154$). According to the bivariate analysis, the coefficient of correlation "r" for Technological knowledge and is equal to 0.824 ($P=0.000$), Creativity of the work force is equal to 0.804 ($p=0.000$), and Technological patents is equal to 0.873 ($P=0.000$). This demonstrates that the dependent variable (Innovation of automobile industry) and the independent variables have positive significance. This therefore underscores that all null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted since the independent variables in the study positively influence innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the management of automobile firms should develop good mechanisms to align their business operations with the current dynamics i.e. adoption of innovation so as to apply new technologies, new techniques and new processes in order to enhance innovation so as to come up with their own automobile brands and commercialize them in the global market. The management should incorporate corporate innovation strategies, technological research and amass automobile production resources in order to enhance innovation of the automobile industry. The government should enact laws and formulate policies that will create an enabling environment for the automobile industry to incorporate innovation so as to come up with their own automobile brands and commercialize them in the global market.

The remaining factors of 12.2% have not been explained by the study leaving room for further research to be conducted.

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